

Samaritan Hymn by Amram Dare

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** Expert Source entry, prepared by a Ph.D. RA or DRH Editor from an expert's published work(s), and then personally edited and approved by the expert.*

Entry tags: Hymn, Religious Group, Abrahamic, Ancient Mediterranean, Poetry, Aramaic, Jewish Traditions, Semitic, Prayer, Text, Northwest Semitic, Afro-Asiatic, Central Semitic, Cosmology, West Semitic, Language, Biblical Prophets

The two texts referred to in this entry are attributed to the priest Amram Dare, the earliest poet of the Samaritan tradition (3rd century CE). However, the earliest manuscript witnesses to these texts date to the 16th and 18th centuries, respectively. These texts are two of the liturgical poems, or piyyutim, which, together with the later addition of prose prayers, compose the Samaritan prayer book, the Defter, which is written in Samaritan Aramaic. The Defter contains a total of 28 poems attributed to Amram Dare, which appear in the section labeled "Hymns (or Liturgies) for the Sabbaths and Festivals." This entry focuses on the hymns known as Amram Dare #6 and Amram Dare #25. The former is a short, lyrical, unrhymed hymn consisting of 33 stichs that emphasizes the uniqueness of God and Moses, while the latter is longer and more structured, consisting of 22 strophes with an embedded acrostic. The second hymn focuses on God's work as creator. Though the ritual occasion for their use in Late Antiquity is not precisely known, in contemporary Samaritan practice the first hymn is recited on Wednesday, the 4th Sabbath of the month, on festivals, and during the week of Shavuot. The second hymn is recited on the morning of the Sabbath and on festivals.

Date Range: 200 CE - 1800 CE

Region: Samaria

Region tags: Samaria, Middle East, Israel, Israel

Samaria

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Lieber, Laura. "Samaritan Hymns by Amram Dare." In *Prayer in the Ancient World*, edited by Daniel K. Falk and Rodney A. Werline. Leiden; Boston: Brill, forthcoming.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://brill.com/display/serial/PAMW?language=en>

Notes: Lieber, Laura. "Samaritan Hymns by Amram Dare." In *Prayer in the Ancient World*, edited by Daniel K. Falk and Rodney A. Werline. Leiden; Boston: Brill, forthcoming.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Notes: The earliest extant copies of the texts date the 16th and 18th centuries, but they are attributed to an individual who lived during the 3rd century CE. How they were transmitted prior to the 16th-18th centuries CE is a matter of speculation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Inked

– with Ink

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Notes: The earliest extant copies of the texts date the 16th and 18th centuries, but they are attributed to an individual who lived during the 3rd century CE.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Specify type of paper

– Specify: Unspecified.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Corrections

Notes: The only notable variations in these texts consist of changes in spelling across manuscripts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: The texts referred to here are part of the Defter, the Samaritan prayer book. They are compliments to scripture within the Samaritan tradition used in religious activities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Depends on the size of the congregation. The texts were, and still are, used by the Samaritan community.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Yes

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– Yes

↳ On the reciter?

– Yes

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– Yes

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?

– Yes

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Does the affect involve unlocking hidden knowledge?
– Yes

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?
– Specify: The texts' contemporary usage is known, but their usage in Late Antiquity nearer to the time of their writing and inclusion in the Defter is not thoroughly known. Whereas these texts are assigned to a particular day and/or festival in their contemporary usage, scholars hypothesize that the priests of the day in Late Antiquity were free to choose these among other poems to complement scriptural readings within a day's rituals.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ On average, how many participants are present?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ How often do the rituals take place?
– Specify: Though the ritual occasion for their use in Late Antiquity is not precisely known, in contemporary Samaritan practice the first hymn is recited on Wednesday, the 4th Sabbath of the month, on festivals, and during the week of Shavuot. The second hymn is recited on the morning of the Sabbath and on festivals.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Yes

Notes: Though the ritual occasion for their use in Late Antiquity is not precisely known, in contemporary Samaritan practice the first hymn is recited on Wednesday, the 4th Sabbath of the month, on festivals, and during the week of Shavuot. The second hymn is recited on the morning of the Sabbath and on festivals.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– No

Notes: Differences between manuscripts are minor, consisting of spelling changes.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– Yes

Notes: The texts form part of the Samaritan Defter, or prayer book.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ How is the authority established?

– Yes

Notes: The two hymns are attributed to a famous priest of Late Antiquity.

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– No

Notes: It is unclear when the Deifter became "closed." In antiquity, prose prayers were added to it over time.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Have major debates shifted the sense of the place of the text with respect to the larger canon?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: The texts are prayers to be read and/or recited aloud.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Text 1 heavily refers to the lineage of Moses, including his father (Amram), mother (Yocheved), and siblings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– Yes

Notes: Yes - in the sense that the lineages referred to in Text 1 are defined by concrete generations.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Supernatural forces

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: Other poems by Amram do relate to the Samaritan festival calendar, which is tied to the calendar described in the Torah as understood by the Samaritans.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

Notes: God is described as a creator, but the text takes care to specify that his works of creation are different from those of humans. However, God also grants mercy, clothes Moses (in clouds), and hears prayers and petitions, which may suggest a certain degree of anthropomorphism.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

Notes: God seems to inhabit the heavens, and clothes Moses in clouds.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

–Specify: God is the creator of all things.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: God is described as omniscient, possessing all knowledge of the world.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Can reward

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Can punish

– Yes

Notes: God's ability to punish is implied by the request for mercy and forgiveness in the second hymn.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Can be hurt?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Can be tricked?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

–Specify: God is the creator of all things.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

Notes: God can be known through observation and appreciation of his creation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ In dreams

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ In trance possession

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Through divination practices

– Yes

Notes: The first hymn describes several prophets (Moses and Miriam).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Other form of communication with living

– Yes

Notes: God can be experienced through His creation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Can the audience communicate directly to gods through the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Can the audience communicate through supernatural intermediaries to the high-god, as a result of the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are there notions of inspiration or inspired knowledge?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Are there rituals required to attain inspired knowledge?

– No

Notes: Knowledge can be gained through observation of God's creation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

What concepts of inspiration exist? (e.g. clairvoyance, insights, vision of the divine world, awareness of divine omnipresent agency or omnipotence, sigh or vision beyond the five senses).

– Yes

Notes: Knowledge can be gained through observation of God's creation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Notes: Other than the supreme high god, no other supernatural beings are present.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Notes: However, the second text suggests that God's presence and nature can be experienced through the observation and appreciation of his creation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: However, prophets are mentioned in the first text.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– No

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - Yes
 - Notes: God will be merciful to those who petition for mercy and forgiveness.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
 - No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Since mercy and forgiveness are requested, presumably the alternative is punishment.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
– No

↳ Done randomly
– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?
– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?
– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
– Yes

↳ Consists of bad luck?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Political failure?
– No

↳ Defeat in battle?
– No

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?
– No

↳ Disaster on journeys?
– No

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?
– No

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?
– No

↳ Sickness or illness?

– No

↳ Impaired reproduction?

– No

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?

– No

↳ Other?

– Specify: The text requests that God not "lock the gates of your mercy in our faces!" The exact consequences are not spelled out beyond this in this text.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Done randomly

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Highly emphasized?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Consists of good luck?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Consists of political success or power?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Consists of success in battle?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Consists of peace or social stability?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Consists of success on journeys?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Other?

– Specify: Happiness is listed as a reward for those in whose heart nothing dwells but God, and who thank God. God is also described as the "rescuer of the oppressed" and the giver of life-breath.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Notes: However, some other poems by Amram do mention a quasi-messianic figure within the Samaritan tradition, the taheb, or "Restorer."

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Amram's tone varies in his poems, so some works stress some virtues other than the virtues emphasized here.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity
– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)
– No

↳ Courage (generic)
– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity
– Yes

- ↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
 - No
- ↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
 - No
- ↳ Respectfulness/courtesy
 - No
- ↳ Familial obedience/filial piety
 - No
- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - Yes
- ↳ Cooperation
 - No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - No
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - No
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - No
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No

- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No
- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - Yes
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
 - Yes
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
 - Yes
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
 - No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text require castration?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Notes: Although taboos on foods are prescribed within the religious culture, they are not present in the text.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Notes: This is not mentioned within the text, but usage of the text is itself a sacrifice of one's time toward ritual devotion to religious life.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: Though explicit ethical precepts are not mentioned, usage of the text implies an agreement with ethics associated with the Samaritan religious tradition.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

What is the average interval of time between performances?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A Segmentary Lineage

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: A learned/scribal elite, perhaps with ties to the priesthood, but not known with any certainty.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Notes: However, in Late Antiquity, education was a male-dominated domain.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– Yes

Notes: There are benefits to knowledge of God through his creation extolled in the second text.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Levant

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